

Nonlinear nanomechanical mass spectrometry without mode-shape identification

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Abstract

Nanomechanical mass spectrometry enables the detection and characterization of individual ionized and neutral particles through resonance-frequency shifts of mechanical resonators. Conventional approaches generally require prior knowledge of resonator mode shapes to determine the mass and location of deposited analytes. However, obtaining accurate mode-shape information becomes increasingly challenging in nanoscale devices, where limited linear dynamic range often leads to strong nonlinear effects that complicate resonance tracking and mass identification.

This work introduces a nonlinear nanomechanical mass spectrometry framework that exploits the nonlinear dynamic response of resonators rather than suppressing it. The proposed approach enables analyte mass determination over a broad range, potentially from daltons to gigadaltons, for resonators of arbitrary geometry without requiring prior knowledge of their vibrational mode shapes. Mass estimation is based solely on shifts in bifurcation frequencies measured in two

consecutive vibration modes. A theoretical model is developed to describe the underlying nonlinear mechanisms and establish the relationship between analyte mass and bifurcation-frequency shifts. The framework is validated experimentally using measurements from a nanomechanical resonator, while Monte Carlo simulations are employed to assess the accuracy and robustness of the mass estimates.

The results demonstrate that nonlinear modal interactions provide sufficient information for accurate mass identification without mode-shape reconstruction, thereby overcoming a key limitation of existing nanomechanical spectrometry methods.

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1. Introduction

Over the past few decades, resonant nanomechanical systems have advanced significantly as platforms for actuation and sensing [1–5]. They are widely used as ultra-high-frequency (> GHz) radiofrequency signal generators [6], probes of quantum systems [7,8], and ultrasensitive detectors of force [9], charge [10], and mass [11]. Their exceptionally high sensitivity, broad linear dynamic range, and relatively operational simplicity make them particularly attractive for nanomechanical mass spectrometry (NEMS spectrometry) [12]. As sensitivity scales with resonance frequency [13], performance has been enhanced through higher-order vibrational modes [14], electrostatic frequency tuning [15,16], and device miniaturization [11,17,18]. Nanoscale resonators, including carbon nanotubes and graphene structures, have reached a near-atomic (Dalton, Da) mass sensitivity [17,19,20]. Unlike conventional mass spectrometers, which require the ionization of the

sample and operate up to kDa [21], exceptionally to tens of MDa [22], multimode NEMS spectrometers can detect both ionized and neutral species [23] and extend the accessible mass range to MDa [24] exceptionally to the GDa regime [25].

In NEMS spectrometry, analyte mass is determined from resonance frequency shifts interpreted using mode-shape models based on beam, membrane, or plate theories, collectively referred to as *mode-shape models* [26–28]. The accuracy of these methods depends critically on precise knowledge of vibrational mode shapes [29]. While reliable at the microscale, these models become increasingly inaccurate at the nanoscale, where fabrication imperfections and/or large analytes (tens of MDa and above) significantly perturb the mode shapes from those expected in idealized structures [30,31]. Moreover, in NEMS spectrometers, mode shapes cannot be directly measured using conventional techniques [32,33], and the reduced linear dynamic range leads to the frequent onset of nonlinearities [34]. These effects complicate resonance tracking and render mode-shape-based mass determination impractical under realistic conditions.

Recent efforts to overcome this limitation include a data-driven “fingerprint” approach proposed by Sader et al. [35], in which analyte mass is determined by matching the frequency shifts across multiple modes with a precomputed database. However, this method requires measurements of several modes (more than 4) and operation strictly within the linear regime, limiting its applicability. In practice, higher-order modes in NEMS spectrometers readily exhibit nonlinearities due to cubic (Duffing-type) restoring forces [36] arising from geometric effects [37] or external field [38]. Although prior work has largely focused on suppressing such nonlinearities [16,34], nonlinear resonators offer intrinsic advantages, including enhanced signal strength, reduced dissipation and improved sensitivity in the presence of noise [36,39–41]. These features

make nonlinear dynamics an attractive, yet underexploited, resource for mass sensing across extreme mass scales.

Existing nonlinear NEMS approaches rely on frequency sweeps [42,43] or bifurcation tracking [44,45]. The former is limited by the elevated frequency noise associated with long sweep durations and the need for frequent parameter resets, whereas the latter one, depends on frequency or amplitude jumps, is mainly suited to specific sample types (e.g., gaseous samples) and does not readily enable a single-mass spectrometry. Closed-loop nonlinear tracking has been demonstrated for single-particle detection [46], but still relies on linear mode-shape models for mass extraction, leading to inaccuracies for large analytes or strong nonlinearities. Consequently, accurate mass determination of large particles such as viruses, bacterial cells, and biomarkers remains a major challenge for both conventional and nanomechanical spectrometry [47]. Hence, the determination of analyte mass in NEMS spectrometry without prior knowledge of vibrational mode shapes, particularly under nonlinear operating conditions and for large analytes, is a key unsolved challenge.

Here, we demonstrate that the analyte mass can be accurately determined from bifurcation jumps in only the first two consecutive resonance frequencies of a NEMS spectrometer. Unlike mode-shape approaches, this method requires no prior knowledge of vibrational modes. In contrast to data-driven approach, it avoids the need for precomputed databases and multi-mode measurements, and, unlike existing nonlinear techniques, it enables direct single-particle mass determination without amplitude tracking or linear approximations. We develop a theoretical framework describing the underlying mechanisms and validate the method using Monte Carlo analysis and reanalysis of experimental data [46] The method remains accurate for large analytes, with relative errors decreasing from ~4% at $m/M = 0.05$ to ~1% at $m/M = 0.4$, where m and M is

the analyte and the resonator mass, respectively. By exploiting, rather than suppressing, nonlinear dynamics, this approach establishes a practical route toward nanomechanical mass spectrometry across extreme mass scales (Da to hundreds of GDa) and opens new opportunities for the characterization of large biological entities.

2. Theory for a single analyte mass sensing with nonlinear NEMS spectrometer

2.1. Developed computational model

Suspended or alternatively cantilevered elastic beams are widely used in NEMS spectrometry. For clarity, we consider a suspended one-dimensional beam with length L , width b , and thickness t_b , as shown in Fig. 1a. Such beams are typically actuated electrostatically [18,19], so that the total displacement consists of a static (DC) component and a time-varying (AC) component [34]. The excitation-induced displacement can be expressed as

$$u_{z,0} = ng/\omega^2, \quad (1)$$

where n is an overload multiple of gravitational acceleration (g) and ω is the angular frequency.

Depending on the excitation amplitude, the system operates either in a weakly or strongly nonlinear regime [36]. Upon adsorption of an analyte of mass m (representing a particle, virus, or bacterial cell) onto the resonator surface at position x_m (see Fig. 1a), the resonator exhibits a shift in bifurcation frequencies (i.e., bifurcation shift), as shown in Fig. 1d. To efficiently capture this behaviour without excessive computational complexity and cost, we model the resonator using quadratic beam elements with a rectangular cross-section (Fig. 1b) (details of the developed model are stored under doi: 10.5281/zenodo.20624227). This approach accurately predicts the amplitude–frequency response of both weakly and strongly nonlinear systems.

For reliable transient analysis, the time-dependent displacement is discretized with at least 100 points per sinusoidal period. The corresponding simulation time step, Δt , is thus given by

$$\Delta t = 1/(100f), \quad (2)$$

where $f = \omega / 2\pi$ is the excitation frequency. Due to symmetry about the midspan, the analyte position x_m is restricted within the range $(0, L/2)$. Structural damping is incorporated via the stiffness-proportional damping model (BETAD command in ANSYS Mechanical APDL). The fundamental analysis forming the theoretical foundation of the developed computational model is detailed in the Appendix.

Fig. 1 a) Schematic of the suspended beam with an analyte attached at position x_m ; b) finite-element representation of the nanomechanical resonator using quadratic beam elements with a rectangular cross-section ($b \times t_b$) employed to predict the nonlinear amplitude–frequency (A - f) response; c) A - f characteristics around the fundamental resonance of the beam exhibiting hardening nonlinearity under different excitation acceleration levels, expressed in units of the

gravitational constant g ; and **d**) shifts in the A-f response near the fundamental frequency induced by the attached analyte mass.

2.2. Method of single analyte mass spectrometry by the nonlinear NEMS spectrometer

The amplitude–frequency response of nonlinear beams differs fundamentally from that of linear systems. In beams exhibiting the Duffing-type nonlinearities[36] and operating in the vicinity of an instability point (see Fig. 1d), even small frequency changes can trigger abrupt transition (jumps) in the oscillation amplitude. Frequency sweeps thus reveal characteristic bifurcation points, namely: i) the jump-up frequency during downward sweeps, and ii) jump-down frequency during upward sweeps. Each bifurcation point is defined by both frequency and amplitude (see Fig. 1c and Fig. 1d). These nonlinear responses depend on the beam's intrinsic properties (e.g., density, Young's modulus, damping) as well as on the analyte mass m and its position x_m . Consequently, bifurcation frequencies contain sufficient information to uniquely determine both parameters (m and x_m), enabling construction of bifurcation-frequency maps over the full parameter space.

The construction of these maps is illustrated schematically for first two consecutive modes during a downward frequency sweep (jump up) in Fig. 2. First, a sufficiently large number of nonlinear transient finite-element simulations were performed to determine the bifurcation frequencies, that is, those at which sudden changes in resonator amplitude occur, for different combinations of normalized positions x_m/L and mass ratios m/M , as also shown for three different scenarios in Fig. 2. Due to the symmetry, only half of the beam domain (as shown by the black points in Fig. 2a and Fig. 2b) was computed, with the second half of the map obtained by mirror reflection. Importantly, all maps coordinates (see Fig. 2) are expressed in normalized form, allowing their application to beams of different scales but of similar material properties.

For systems with significantly different material parameters, new bifurcation maps accounting for their specific characteristics (e.g., stiffness, damping, or density) must be generated to avoid substantial errors in analyte mass determination. An analytical approximation of these maps, elucidating the physical principles underlying the proposed method, is presented in the Appendix.

Fig. 2 Bifurcation frequency maps of a suspended beam as functions of the analyte-to-beam mass ratio (m/M) and analyte attachment position (x_m/L) for (a) the first and (b) the second mode and downward frequency sweep; here numbers 0, 1 and 2 on x -axis label stand for three different configurations (i.e. 0 stands for Conf., 1 stands for Conf. 1 and 2 represents Conf. 2); f_u means the jump up bifurcation frequency.

The mass of the analyte, m , is determined by comparing bifurcation jumps of the unloaded resonator, $f_{no\ mass}$, with those measured after analyte adsorption, f_{exp} . The method requires at least

two distinct bifurcation jumps, such as the jump-up and jump-down frequencies of the fundamental mode, or those of the first two consecutive vibrational modes. Notably, larger differences in the bifurcation maps were observed for different vibrational modes (e.g., the first vs. second) yielding the higher accuracy in the estimated analyte mass.

To quantify this, bifurcation frequencies are expressed as ratios ($f_{exp}/f_{no\ mass}$) for each mode, enabling construction of two plane cuts through the corresponding bifurcation maps (Fig. 3a–d). Combining these two cuts in a single 2D plot reveals intersection points corresponding to the mass ratio m/M (Fig. 3e); from which the analyte mass, m , can be accurately determined. For practical implementation, the intersection curves may be interpolated using suitable functions to accurately extract the mass ratio and thereby identify the analyte.

2.3. Comparison with mode-shape-based approaches

As shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 (a,c), the proposed nonlinear mass-sensing method shares certain conceptual similarities with conventional mode-shape-based approaches. In both cases, adsorption of an analyte onto the resonator leads to a reduction in resonance (or bifurcation) frequencies, with mass determined from two consecutive resonance (or bifurcation) frequencies measured before and after adsorption. However, unlike conventional mode-shape methods, the present nonlinear approach requires no prior knowledge or experimental measurement of the mode shapes. Furthermore, unlike previous nonlinear techniques[46], it does not rely on the amplitude measurements. This represents a significant advantage, particularly for relatively large masses ($m/M > 0.02$), where the presence of the analyte substantially perturbs the mode shapes of the resonator. Under such conditions, conventional mode-shape models become inaccurate, and precise amplitude measurements are often difficult to obtain in nonlinear regimes.

To highlight the key differences between the present nonlinear method and commonly used mode-shape models, we consider four representative analytes with mass ratios $m/M = 0.01, 0.1, 0.25,$ and 0.5 attached at positions $x = 0.25L$ and $x = 0.4L$ on an identical silicon beam resonator operating under nonlinear excitation ($500g$), corresponding to a Duffing-type regime. The results, summarized in Table 1, demonstrate the clear advantage of the nonlinear method over conventional mode-shape-based approaches. The inaccuracies of the nonlinear method are primarily associated with second-order interpolation errors in the maps, whereas errors in the mode-shape-approaches originate from deviations in the assumed mode shapes due to the combined effects of analyte mass and structural nonlinearity. As a result, the accuracy of the mode-shape models deteriorates with increasing nonlinearity or analyte mass. Moreover, as shown in Table 1, applying mode-shape-based analysis to nonlinear NEMS spectrometer (an approach previously attempted by Yuksel et al.[46]) can lead to substantial errors in the estimated mass. In contrast, the present nonlinear framework maintains high accuracy under these conditions and is therefore better suited for mass spectrometry of large analytes and systems operating beyond the linear regime.

Table 1. Comparison of the accuracy in determining analyte mass using the standard mode-shape model and our nonlinear model for a NEMS spectrometer operating in the nonlinear regime

	Analyte position	Analyte to beam mass ratio			
		0.01	0.1	0.25	0.5
Mode-shape model	$x = 0.25L$	0.0048 (48%)	0.051 (50%)	0.15 (40%)	0.35 (30%)
	$x = 0.4L$	0.0088 (13%)	0.089 (11%)	0.19 (22%)	0.39 (22%)
Nonlinear method	$x = 0.25L$	0.00106 (6%)	0.105 (5%)	0.2575 (3%)	0.51 (2%)
	$x = 4L$	0.01025 (3%)	0.1028 (3%)	0.2526 (1%)	0.5047 (1%)

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

Fig. 3 (a - d) Plane cuts through bifurcation-frequency maps showing jump-up frequencies for the first (a, b) and second (c, d) resonant modes; **e)** combined plane cuts from **(a - d)** with intersection point(s) revealing the analyte mass ratio (m/M); $f_{u \text{ mass}}$ and $f_{u \text{ no mass}}$ denote measured bifurcation frequencies with and without analyte, m and M stand for the analyte and beam masses, respectively.

3. Results and discussion

We validate the proposed nonlinear single-analyte mass sensing method using the Monte-Carlo simulations and by reanalyzing the previously reported experimental data on gold nanoparticle adsorption onto a suspended SiN nanomechanical resonator [46]. In general, the accuracy of the determined analyte mass depends on the error in the measured frequencies of the nanomechanical resonator. Unlike conventional linear nanomechanical mass spectrometry, where accuracy decreases for mass ratios $m/M > 0.02$ [29,30] due to violations of the mode shape assumptions, the proposed nonlinear method exhibits improved accuracy with increasing analyte mass. This behavior arises because larger analytes induce more pronounced shifts in bifurcation jumps thereby enhancing the distinguishability between the loaded and unloaded resonator states.

To demonstrate this fact and to also assess the impact of measurement errors across a broad range of analyte masses (i.e., light ~kDa, medium ~MDa and heavy ~GDa), we performed the Monte Carlo analysis for two different instrumental error levels (250 Hz and 500 Hz). The results are summarized in Table 2 and

Table 3. For a given measurement uncertainty, the relative error in the estimated mass decreases with increasing mass ratio, reaching values as low as ~1% for $m/M = 0.4$.

Table 2. The achievable accuracy in the determined analyte mass m and its relative (i.e., from the clamped ends) position of attachment x_m/L for different analyte masses and the frequency measurement error of ± 250 Hz obtained from the MC analysis. The mass of the resonator is $M = 2.52$ ag for $m/M = 0.05$, $M = 252$ ag for $m/M = 0.1$, and $M = 25.2$ fg for $m/M = 0.4$, respectively.

Mass ratio m/M [-]	Analyte position x_m/L [-]	Estimated values for uncertainties in the measured frequency of 250 Hz.			Maximum absolute error in determined values [%]	
		x_m/L [-]	m/M [-]	m	m/M	x_m/L
0.05	0.2	0.2 ± 0.019	0.05 ± 0.006	75.9 ± 8.8 [kDa]	12.4	9.8
	0.3	0.3 ± 0.008	0.05 ± 0.002	75.9 ± 3.3 [kDa]	4.1	2.7
	0.45	0.45 ± 0.006	0.05 ± 0.002	75.9 ± 3.3 [kDa]	4.3	1.4
0.1	0.2	0.2 ± 0.009	0.1 ± 0.005	15.2 ± 0.9 [MDa]	5.3	4.8
	0.3	0.3 ± 0.004	0.1 ± 0.002	15.2 ± 0.3 [MDa]	2.2	1.4
	0.45	0.45 ± 0.003	0.1 ± 0.003	15.2 ± 0.4 [MDa]	3.6	0.7
0.4	0.2	0.2 ± 0.003	0.4 ± 0.006	6.1 ± 0.09 [GDa]	1.4	1.6
	0.3	0.3 ± 0.002	0.4 ± 0.003	6.1 ± 0.04 [GDa]	0.7	0.5
	0.45	0.45 ± 0.001	0.4 ± 0.003	6.1 ± 0.05 [GDa]	0.9	0.2

Table 3. The achievable accuracy in the determined analyte mass m and its relative (i.e., from the clamped ends) position of attachment x_m/L for different analyte masses and the frequency measurement error of ± 500 Hz obtained from the MC analysis. The mass of the resonators is $M = 2.52$ ag for $m/M = 0.05$, $M = 252$ ag for $m/M = 0.1$, and $M = 25.2$ fg for $m/M = 0.4$, respectively.

Mass ratio m/M [-]	Analyte position x_m/L [-]	Estimated values for uncertainties in the measured frequency of 500 Hz.			Maximum absolute error in determined values [%]	
		x_m/L [-]	m/M [-]	m	m/M	x_m/L
0.05	0.2	0.02 ± 0.042	0.05 ± 0.018	75.9 ± 27 [kDa]	39.8	21.8
	0.3	0.3 ± 0.017	0.05 ± 0.004	75.9 ± 6 [kDa]	8.3	5.6
	0.45	0.45 ± 0.013	0.05 ± 0.004	75.9 ± 6 [kDa]	8.6	2.9
0.1	0.2	0.2 ± 0.0192	0.1 ± 0.012	15.2 ± 1.6 [MDa]	12.6	9.9
	0.3	0.3 ± 0.009	0.1 ± 0.004	15.2 ± 0.6 [MDa]	4.6	2.9
	0.45	0.45 ± 0.007	0.1 ± 0.007	15.2 ± 0.9 [MDa]	7.3	1.5
0.4	0.2	0.2 ± 0.005	0.4 ± 0.01	6.1 ± 0.15 [GDa]	2.7	2.8
	0.3	0.3 ± 0.003	0.4 ± 0.005	6.1 ± 0.07 [GDa]	1.3	1.0
	0.45	0.45 ± 0.002	0.4 ± 0.007	6.1 ± 0.10 [GDa]	1.7	0.4

This trend can be understood from the geometry of the cuts of bifurcation-frequency maps (Fig. 3e) and Fig. 4). For larger mass ratios, the intersection angles between the corresponding curves become smaller, resulting in more localized and robust intersection regions even in the presence of frequency noise. Whilst, for smaller masses or higher measurement uncertainties, the intersection regions broaden, leading to increased uncertainty in the extracted mass and position. These effects are illustrated in Fig. 4, where the grey regions represent the variability induced by

frequency measurement errors. Importantly, for mass ratios $m/M > 0.2$, the nonlinear method maintains high accuracy across most of the resonator length, with reduced performance only near the clamped ends (Fig. 5). This represents a substantial improvement over conventional linear approaches, which exhibit rapidly increasing errors in this regime [30].

Fig. 4 The graphical illustration of the sought analyte mass and its relative position of attachment using the Monte-Carlo analysis for frequency errors of ± 250 Hz and ± 500 Hz and **a)** $m/M = 0.05$ and $x_m/L = 0.3$; **b)** $m/M = 0.1$ and $x_m/L = 0.2$; **c)** $m/M = 0.4$ and $x_m/L = 0.3$; **d)** $m/M = 0.4$ and $x_m/L = 0.45$. Grey areas determine variation and uncertainties in the determined analyte mass and attachment position concerning the frequency measurement error.

Fig. 5 The achievable accuracy in the determined analyte represented through the mass ratio, m/M , for different analyte relative positions of attachment, x_m/L , and instrumental errors.

To further validate the method, we reanalyzed experimental data reported previously for gold nanoparticle adsorption on a prestressed SiN resonator (100 nm thick, 320 nm width, and 20 μm long) exhibiting Duffing-type nonlinearities [46]. In the original study, mass estimation relied on

mode-shape-based analysis of resonance frequency shifts. Here, we instead extract the analyte mass from bifurcation-frequency maps using shifts measured in the first two vibrational modes. The relative frequency jumps $\Delta f_n/f_{0n}$ for mass determination were obtained from data given in the Supplementary Information of [46]. For the first two adsorption events, the first mode jumps were $\sim -0.152 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (1st event) and $-0.27 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (2nd event) and the second mode jumps were $0.348 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (1st event) and $-0.506 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (2nd event). Then, intersections in bifurcation-frequency maps (see Fig. 6) from these jumps reveal possible attachment positions and, subsequently, mass ratios. For event 1 the possible position of attachment ~ 0.24 or 0.76 (i.e., midspan symmetry) and mass ~ 41.5 MDa (~ 19 nm diameter) were obtained. Similarly, for event 2 the particle mass ~ 59.2 MDa and diameter of ~ 21.4 nm were determined. The obtained gold nanoparticle mass and the size are in good agreement with the mass spectra presented in Fig. 4 of Ref. [46] (i.e., both nanoparticle mass and its diameter are within the region of the statistical distribution of these parameters). Minor discrepancies in the obtained nanoparticle masses (sizes) can be attributed primarily to the coarse resolution of the bifurcation-frequency maps used in the present analysis, suggesting that further fine refinement of the mapping procedure could yield even higher accuracy.

These results demonstrate that the proposed nonlinear method enables robust and accurate mass determination across a wide range of analyte sizes, including regimes where conventional methods fail. By leveraging nonlinear dynamics rather than avoiding them, the method provides a powerful and practical route toward nanomechanical mass spectrometry of large biological entities and complex nanoscale systems.

Fig. 6 Combined plane cuts in the bifurcation-frequency maps obtained for the first two events of Table S1 (supplementary Information of [46]) used to determine the gold nanoparticle position of attachment, mass, and its size (diameter); for an event **a**) no. 1 $m = 47.5$ MDa and diameter of ~ 19 nm, and **b**) no. 2 $m = 59.2$ MDa and diameter of ~ 21.4 nm, respectively.

4. Conclusions

A nonlinear nanomechanical mass-sensing framework has been developed that eliminates the need for prior knowledge of resonator mode shapes and operation within the linear dynamic regime. The method exploits shifts in bifurcation frequencies to determine analyte mass from measurements of two consecutive vibration modes, without requiring mode-shape reconstruction or amplitude-based characterization. Owing to its formulation, the approach is applicable to resonators of arbitrary geometry and extends nanomechanical mass spectrometry over a broad mass range spanning several orders of magnitude, potentially from the Dalton to the gigadalton regime.

A theoretical model describing the relationship between analyte mass and bifurcation-frequency shifts has been established and validated through numerical and experimental investigations. The results demonstrate that nonlinear dynamic features provide sufficient information for accurate mass estimation and that the achievable accuracy is maintained, and in

some cases improved, for larger analytes, where conventional mode-shape-based approaches become increasingly challenging [29].

The present study shows that nonlinear bifurcation dynamics can be systematically utilized for mass identification in nanomechanical resonators. More broadly, the proposed framework provides a basis for the development of mode-shape-independent sensing strategies and contributes to the understanding of particle-induced perturbations in nonlinear resonating systems. These findings expand the applicability of nanomechanical mass spectrometry to complex analytes and operating conditions where nonlinear effects cannot be neglected.

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Data availability

Regarding the computational procedures and bifurcation frequency maps data, see Ševeček, O., Skalka, P., et al. (2026). Dataset for "Harnessing nonlinearity for mode-shape independent nanomechanical mass spectrometry across extreme mass scales (from Da to GDa) " (1.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20624227>.

Appendix

We consider a doubly clamped elastic beam subjected to a harmonic base displacement $w_b = w_{b0} \sin \omega t$ and with an additional mass m at an arbitrary position x_m . The beam is assumed to exhibit linear internal (material) damping, as well as the geometric nonlinearity arising from the mid-plane stretching, which induces an extension ΔL in the length of the beam. Then, according to the Euler-Bernoulli theory, the partial differential equation describing the transverse displacement $w(x, t)$ with respect to the prescribed displacement of its ends is:

$$\left[\frac{M}{L} + m\delta(x - x_m) \right] \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} + EI \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + c_s I \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^4} \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} - \frac{ES}{2L} \int_0^L \left[\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 dx \right] \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} = \left[\frac{M}{L} + m\delta(x - x_m) \right] w_{b0} \omega^2 \sin \omega t, \quad (\text{A1})$$

with boundary conditions

$$w(0, t) = w(L, t) = \frac{\partial w(0, t)}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial w(L, t)}{\partial x} = 0, \quad (\text{A2})$$

where M is the beam mass, L is its length, m is the additional mass attached to the beam at an arbitrary position x_m , EI is the flexural rigidity, I is the moment of inertia, S is the area of the beam's cross section, c_s is the coefficient representing internal damping mechanisms, ω is the angular frequency and w_{b0} stands for the resonator base displacement amplitude. Apparently, the presence of geometric nonlinearity renders Eq. (A1) intrinsically nonlinear.

The internal damping described by the term $c_s I \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^4} \frac{\partial w}{\partial t}$ is caused by an internal force

which reacts against the variation of the curvature with time. To decouple the equation of motion into an infinite set of modal coordinates $q_n(t)$ and mode shapes $\phi_n(x)$, the displacement is written by making use of separation of variables:

$$w_n(x,t) = q_n(t)\phi_n(x) \quad (\text{A3})$$

Assuming that the beam is vibrating predominantly in one of these eigenmodes and use this assumption to evaluate the effective Duffing parameter α_n , multiplying the q_n^3 term in the equation of motion for this mode. Multiplying Eq. (A1) by the chosen eigenmode $\phi_n(x)$ and integrate over x to get, after some integration by parts, a Duffing equation of motion for the amplitude of the n^{th} mode $q_n(t)$ can be written as

$$m_n \frac{d^2 q_n}{dt^2} + \Gamma_n \frac{dq_n}{dt} + m_n \omega_{0n}^2 q_n + \alpha_n q_n^3 = m_n w_{b0} \omega^2 \sin \omega t, \quad (\text{A4})$$

where

$$m_n = \frac{M}{L} \int_0^L \phi_n^2 dx + m \phi_n^2(x_m), \quad \Gamma_n = c_s I \int_0^L \phi_n''^2 dx, \quad m_n \omega_{0n}^2 = EI \int_0^L \phi_n''^2 dx, \quad \alpha_n = \frac{ES}{2L} \left(\int_0^L \phi_n'^2 dx \right)^2 \quad (\text{A5})$$

It is convenient to express Eq. (A4) in the dimensionless form and solve it using secular perturbation theory. Keeping only the first perturbative correction, the solution to the Eq. (A4) can be obtained as

$$q_n(t) \approx q_{n0} \sin(\omega t + \psi_n) \quad (\text{A6})$$

where

$$q_{n0}^2 = \frac{\left(\frac{w_{b0} \omega^2}{2\omega_{0n}^2} \right)^2}{\left(\frac{\omega - \omega_{0n}}{\omega_{0n}} - \frac{3}{8} \frac{\alpha_n}{m_n \omega_{0n}^2} q_{n0}^2 \right)^2 + \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{\Gamma_n}{m_n \omega_{0n}} \right)^2}, \quad \tan \psi_n = \frac{\frac{\Gamma_n}{2}}{m_n (\omega - \omega_{0n}) - \frac{3\alpha_n}{8\omega_{0n}} q_{n0}^2}. \quad (\text{A7})$$

The condition for resonance, where the magnitude of the response is at its peak, is found by requiring $dq_{n0}^2/d\omega = 0$. The resonance frequency $\omega_{n\max}$ depends quadratically on the peak magnitude $q_{n0\max}$ as

$$\omega_{n\max} = \omega_{0n} + \frac{3}{8} \frac{\alpha_n}{m_n \omega_{0n}} q_{n0\max}^2 \quad (\text{A8})$$

To elucidate the origin of the bifurcation frequency maps in Fig. 2., we analyze Eq. (A7) for two saddle-node bifurcation points, where the number of solutions changes from one to three and vice versa. At these points $d\omega/dq_{n0}^2 = 0$. To further simplify mathematical expressions, consider that the excitation amplitude approaches a critical value where the two bifurcation points merge into an inflection point. At this point both $d\omega/dq_{n0}^2 = 0$ and $d^2\omega/(dq_{n0}^2)^2 = 0$, providing two equations for determining the critical condition for the onset of bistability, or the existence of two stable solution branches. The critical angular frequency ω_{nu} corresponding to the frequency $f_{nu, mass}$ ($n=1,2$) in Fig. 2 then reads

$$\omega_{nu} = \omega_{0n} + \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} \frac{c_s I \int_0^L \phi_n^{n^2} dx}{M \left(\frac{1}{L} \int_0^L \phi_n^2 dx + \frac{m}{M} \phi_n^2(x_m) \right)}. \quad (\text{A9})$$

The ratio $f_{nu, mass}/f_{nu, no mass}$ ($n = 1,2$) in Fig. 2 can then be expressed as

$$\frac{f_{nu, mass}}{f_{nu, no mass}} = \frac{\left(\frac{EI \int_0^L \phi_n^{n^2} dx}{M \left(\frac{1}{L} \int_0^L \phi_n^2 dx + \frac{m}{M} \phi_n^2(x_m) \right)} \right)^{1/2} + \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} \frac{c_s I \int_0^L \phi_n^{n^2} dx}{M \left(\frac{1}{L} \int_0^L \phi_n^2 dx + \frac{m}{M} \phi_n^2(x_m) \right)}}{\left(\frac{EI \int_0^L \phi_n^{n^2} dx}{\frac{M}{L} \int_0^L \phi_n^2 dx} \right)^{1/2} + \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} \frac{c_s I \int_0^L \phi_n^{n^2} dx}{\frac{M}{L} \int_0^L \phi_n^2 dx}} \quad (A10)$$

The expression on the right-hand side of Eq. (A10) exhibits all the basic features of the characteristic bifurcation frequency maps in Fig. 2, i.e. a decrease in the $f_{nu, mass} / f_{nu, no mass}$ ratio with increasing mass ratio m/M , a dependence on the vibrational mode shape, and a dependence on an additional mass position. It is important to emphasize that the mode shapes $\phi_n(x)$ in the presence of an attached mass generally differ from those of the unloaded beam. In the present analysis, however, the mode shapes serve only as a mathematical construct to elucidate the physical origin of the bifurcation-frequency maps obtained numerically. Their explicit knowledge is not required for practical implementation of the proposed mass-determination method.

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